

New combinations in *Odontochilus* (Orchidaceae)

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Abstract: Four new combinations are proposed under the genus *Odontochilus* Blume. These nomenclatural changes are required to align species formerly placed in *Kuhlhasseltia* J.J.Sm. and *Myrmechis* Blume with the current taxonomic concept of *Odontochilus*, as supported by recent molecular phylogenetic studies.

Keywords: China, *Kuhlhasseltia motuoensis*, *Myrmechis brachyscapa*, *Myrmechis lingulata*, *Myrmechis longii*, Tibet, Vietnam

Introduction

Recent molecular phylogenetic studies have resulted in substantial changes to generic delimitation within Orchidaceae. Phylogenetic analyses of the subtribe Goodyerinae demonstrate that *Evrardianthe* Rauschert, *Kuhlhasseltia* J.J.Sm., *Myrmechis* Blume, *Pristiglottis* Cretz. & J.J.Sm. and *Vexillabium* F.Maek. are nested within *Odontochilus* Blume (Yukawa, 2016; Chen et al., 2019). In order to maintain a monophyletic *Odontochilus* and to comply with the current taxonomic concept of the genus, *Kuhlhasseltia motuoensis* X.H.Jin & C.Ye, *Myrmechis brachyscapa* Aver., Vuong & Ormerod, *Myrmechis lingulata* J.D.Ya, Ting Zhang & C.Liu and *Myrmechis longii* J.D.Ya are here transferred to *Odontochilus*.

New combinations

Odontochilus motuoensis (X.H.Jin & C.Ye) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Kuhlhasseltia motuoensis* X.H.Jin & C.Ye, *Phytotaxa* 626(2): 141. 2023.

Holotype: Tibet, Motuo County, 1300 m, 1 August 2023, *X.H. Jin et al.* 40400 (PE).

Distribution: Tibet.

Odontochilus brachyscapus (Aver., Vuong & Ormerod) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Myrmechis brachyscapa* Aver., Vuong & Ormerod, *Phytotaxa* 619(4): 260. 2023.

Holotype: Vietnam, Ha Giang Province, Vi Xuyen district, Minh Tan Commune, c 1000 m, 14 May 2023, T.B. Vuong & V.D. Thao s.n. (VNMN).

Distribution: Vietnam.

Odontochilus lingulatus (J.D.Ya, Ting Zhang & C.Liu) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Myrmechis lingulata* J.D.Ya, Ting Zhang & C.Liu, *Pl. Diversity* 43(5): 364. 2021.

Holotype: China, Sichuan, Aba Prefecture, Jiuzhaigou County, Wujiao Town, 2508 m, 15 July 2019, T. Zhang et al. 19CS18360 (KUN).

Distribution: China (Sichuan).

Odontochilus longii (J.D.Ya) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Myrmechis longii* J.D.Ya, *Pl. Diversity* 43(5): 365. 2021.

Holotype: China, Yunnan, Wenshan Prefecture, Malipo County, 1500 m, 21 July 2020, J.D. Ya, M.F. Long, M.J. Feng & M.Q. Han 20CS19132 (KUN).

Distribution: China (Yunnan).

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